

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“IN TIMES OF NEED”

It warms my heart to see
How we, as Filipinos, stand together
In thought, in word, and in deed
Chasing one shared dream:
The success of our nation.

It is beautiful to witness
People working hand in hand,
Not only for themselves,
But for the good of everyone.
Each effort, each small act of care,
Becomes a light for others to follow.

To those who were chosen to serve,
May you always remember
The promises once spoken
Before the people who trusted you.

Let us give strength and voice
To those still hoping
That one day, we will rise again
From the grip of poverty
That holds us down
Through neglect and unfairness.

Like the projects built for all
Schools, bridges, hospitals,
Shelters for safety in storms
Let us make sure no one is left behind
When hardships come upon us.

But it hurts to see
That in times of disaster,
When earthquakes strike or floods destroy,
So many lives are lost and broken.
And worse still,
We often lose our unity,
Quarreling instead of helping one another.
How long will this continue?

I still believe
That the true strength of our nation
Will only be found
When we learn to help,
To yield, and to love one another.

Let us move forward as one,
Not because we think alike, or support the same leaders
But because we are Filipinos.
And no matter what comes,
Our **bayanihan** spirit
Will always rise above all.

May we stay united,
Bound together in peace and hope
Yesterday, today, and forevermore.

